

“An Empirical Study on Business Management Students Perception at Undergraduate Level on Online Shopping & Digital Marketing as an Opportunity for Startups with Special Reference to Bangalore District”

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: August

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Shivakumar, and Virupaksha. “An Empirical Study on Business Management Students Perception at Undergraduate Level on Online Shopping & Digital Marketing as an Opportunity for Startups with Special Reference to Bangalore District.” *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 40-44.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3371271>

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Abstract

On 1st July, 2015 our honorable prime minister of India implemented digital India. The objective of this is to digitalize all governmental transactions with the help of electronic networks and improving digital literacy. Today various opportunities to purchase a product, getting offers and discounts, etc. In order to develop brand awareness and perception for all business entities most significant factors is consumer perception. It is essential for the management to understand consumer perception more effectively and efficiently through both online and offline marketing. This paper covers awareness of online shopping among business management students and factors influencing their usage. This also focuses on efforts of the government for educating the society towards online shopping. This paper is based on empirical research conducted on business management students of various colleges at Bangalore district and also concentrates on factors affecting online shopping. The research is done using primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected from 125 respondents by using questionnaire method with the help of Google form. In this paper we have used graph, chart to analyze the data and SPSS software to test one way ANOVA and factor analysis. After analysis and interpretation, the students' perception in Bangalore city reveals that the percentage of respondents are influenced through website to do online shopping and from the study majority of the respondents who are aware about online shopping and are using internet marketing between the age group of below 25 years.

Key Words: Digital marketing, students perception, Awareness of online shopping.

Introduction

Today, the term internet is the most important tool for different types of business. It acts as a mediator between buyer and seller. It is a public,

cooperative and self-sustaining facility to millions of individual worldwide. The early willingness of customers to online shopping influenced by life of the product, price, quality and transactional security, informational technology education. The customer's view on online shopping varies from person to person and the perception is limited to a certain extent with the availability of the proper connectivity and exposure to the buying online. some times the perception of the customers has also parallels and difference based on their personal attitude and characteristics. The factors that influenced online shopping need to be very carefully concerned by online vendors. the study reveals that elder people don't use online shopping as compare to youngsters because youngsters are more attached to online shopping.

Review of Literature

According to Dr.R.Shanthi, Dr. DestiKannaiah (2015), the most of the youngsters are involved to the online shopping.the younger ones use online shopping more as compare to elder people. The age of 20-25 are frequently composed to use the online shopping is the highlights of the study.

Peterson et al. (1997) in his study explained that the starting point of the consumer,the characteristics of the product in question and market structure will be influenced by decision sequences.consumer's attitude towards online shopping is a noticeable factor affecting actual buying behavior.

According to Vidya S Gurav, Vinay R Patil (2016) In his study found that due to advancement of technology , growth of internet and awareness of advantages of online shopping all age classes of customers prefer online shopping. It can be decided that Cost saving the most important factors consider by people to purchase online.

According to ManishaKinker and N.K. Shukla(2016) observed that the main specific factors influence customers attitudes towards online shopping as follows time saving, product quality, product price, convenience, accessibility, shop any where and any time.

According to Kapoor (2012), In his study commented that online shopping sensations and decision making are ruled by a number of customer acceptance and behavior features and grounded in theoretical aspects of customer decision making. There are various number of aspects that affect what, when and why we buy with regard to online shopping.some of the important factors influence that consumers are marketing efforts, psychological factors, socio cultural influence,personalquestions,post decision behavior and experience.

Statement of Problem

Digitalization the most important dream goal of government. Government has to frame proper strategies from time to time for completely digitalization.in the present modern era almost every individual using internet and smart phones.but most of the people using internet for the purpose of social media like youtube, telegram, twitter, facebook, what'app etc.. and only few number of persons are using internet for online shopping by undergraduate level students .hence there is a requirement of the study to find out how many number of persons aware about online shopping and how many number not aware and this study is done only in Bangalore district.

Objective of the Study

1. To find out the students perception towards online purchase and digital marketing..
2. To know the factors influencing students to buy online.
3. To know the awareness level of students towards online shopping.

Scope of the Study

1. Useful for the future reference.
2. Useful to Government to know the functioning of the online shopping through internet.

Research Methodology

The present research study is an Empirical research conducted among the students of B.Com/ BBA/BCA awareness towards online shopping. The study is accomplished with the help of structured questionnaire circulated among under graduate students with help of students of our college. In our study we used structured questionnaire for collecting primary data with help of google form. Secondary data used for review of literature includes the research publications which are enclosed in the references.

Sample Design of the Study

- Sample size: The study was based on the 125 respondents which was chosen purposively and conveniently.
- Coverage of the study: the study is restricted to undergraduate students.
- Sampling technique: Probability sampling is where simple random sampling is used for collecting the data, where respondents are selected as per my wish and my convenience.

Techniques for Analysing Data

Data Analysis is done by using graphs and tables which are analyzed through Ms. Excel and SPSS.

Limitation of the Study

1. The study is confined to select undergraduate students only.
2. The study is confined to Bangalore district in India.
3. The study will not concentrate on technical issue in digital marketing.

Data Presentation from the Primary Data Collected (Findings)

H0: There is no significant difference between opinion of students on practical syllabus on online shopping and perceiving Online marketing as new business opportunities.

H1: There is significant difference between opinion of students on practical syllabus on online shopping and perceiving Online marketing as new business opportunities.

ANOVA					
NEP					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.611	1	1.611	2.254	.136
Within Groups	90.777	127	.715		
Total	92.388	128			

Findings

1. From the above analysis it is found that null hypothesis is accepted as the p value 0.136 is greater than 0.05. So it is found that There is no significant difference between opinion of students on practical syllabus on online shopping and perceiving Online marketing as new business opportunities.
2. It is also found that still few percentages of students are not aware of digital marketing completely.
3. Few students have not adopted online shopping though they are aware of this.
4. Few students are of opinion that they are not satisfied with the quality of products which they purchase online.
5. It is also found that few percentage of students feel that the websites are not user friendly.
6. But students perceive it as new business opportunity and few of the respondents are also of opinion that they have practical syllabus on it.

Suggestions

1. It is suggested that syllabus of under graduation should give practical exposure to the students.
2. The websites are to be designed in user friendly manner.
3. Products offered online should give real time shopping experience that is quality should be same as they perceive that online.
4. Syllabus on online shopping should also include some workshops where the students can have opportunities for startups.
5. More security measures are to be implemented as the many students are still not adopting online shopping though they are aware of it.
6. Awareness on online shopping should be focused as the many students are not aware of online shopping.

Conclusion

In this study it can be concluded that commerce and management students are to be made completely aware of online shopping by framing practical oriented syllabus... the government should take proper measures to overcome above problems of security , infrastructure etc...

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